

Single-chamber microbial fuel cell and anaerobic digestion for the energetic valorization of household food wastes

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In the present study the valorisation of typical household food waste (HFW) was studied via its bioconversion to electricity through a microbial fuel cell (MFC). HFW was produced at municipality level and was heat dried and shredded upon collection. Drying and shredding were applied in order to prevent the biodegradation of the waste and to ensure its stable and unchanging composition during its storage. Dried HFW (DHFH) was initially subjected to extraction using warm water resulting to a liquid fraction (extract) and a solid residue. The extraction process was initially optimized so as to obtain the maximum concentration of soluble compounds (i.e. sugars, acids, amino acids), achieving thus the highest possible soluble chemical oxygen demand (sCOD) of the extract. The rich in sCOD extract was forwarded for electricity production through a four air-cathodes single chamber MFC, operating at 28 °C, while the remaining solid fraction produced from the extraction process was used as substrate for methane production via anaerobic digestion (AD). The MFC was initially operated in batch mode using a synthetic nutrient solution based on glucose and then the reactor operation was switched to continuous mode and the effect of the hydraulic retention time (HRT) was investigated. In the sequel, glucose was replaced by the DHFH extract and a stable long term operation of the MFC was achieved. The effect of the operational parameters such as the HRT and the organic loading rate was also studied, aiming at exploring the possibility of achieving a stable and successful operation, under the highest possible initial concentration of soluble COD. In order to perform a detailed electrochemical characterization of the MFC, its impedance characteristics were also investigated by conducting Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) experiments using either glucose or DHFH extract as substrates. Thus, the effect of both substrates on the internal resistance R_{in} of the MFC was assessed under open and closed circuit conditions and the specific electrochemical characteristics of the MFC were correlated to the MFC performance. The possibility of using AD for the solid residue from the extraction process was tested at 35 °C via biochemical methane potential (BMP) experiments. Energy inputs and outputs were estimated based on the operational conditions of both reactors (MFC and BMP experiments) and the overall energy balances of a whole process were assessed. The results of the study indicated that the exploitation of the DHFH is quite appealing leading to promising energy recovery.